

VEILS, MATS & TISSUES
FOR NON-STRUCTURAL APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

Nonwoven materials produced by a variation of papermaking techniques can be made from a number of fibres including carbon, aramid and glass. The use of such nonwovens in composites is discussed with particular reference to the modification of non structural properties. The areas of surface finishing, fire protection, electrical conductivity, EMI/RFI shielding and chemical resistance, are discussed and practical examples are given of some of these.

INTRODUCTION

Papermaking or wet-laid nonwoven production is essentially the deposition of a random mass of fibre from a liquid slurry on a continuously moving mesh. The fibre slurry requires fairly short fibres (up to 25 mm) to produce an even dispersion. The web produced from this slurry is a mesh of short fibres with a totally random arrangement within the plane of the sheet. (Fig. 1)

(Fig. 1) SEM Carbon Fibre Nonwoven x 640

Nonwovens are produced with areal weights from around 20 g/m² the lighter weight materials are often known as veils or tissues, the heavier weights are often termed 'felts'.

Papermaking has traditionally used cellulosic fibres which form strong inter-fibre bonds by hydrogen bonding after mechanical treatment in water, this mechanism is not possible with synthetic fibres, so a chemical binder must be used to maintain the sheet structure. Binders can be selected for a wide range of chemical groups to suit the end use of the product. Of particular importance when used in polyester composites is the ability of the binder to dissolve or to remain stable in styrene. Nonwoven hybrids can contain any desired proportion of the constituents, the sheet consisting of two interpenetrating random fibre networks. (Fig. 2)

(Fig. 2) SEM Hybrid Carbon/Cellulose Fibre Nonwoven x 38

COMPOSITE PRODUCTION

Nonwovens can be used in any of the composite production techniques which employ sheet materials. Lighter weight nonwovens behave like surfacing tissue whereas the heavier weights are similar to chopped strand mat. The material can be cut to size for continuous processes such as SMC production or pultrusion or die stamped for repeat operations requiring complex shapes e.g. R.I.M.

Binders which are soluble in the resin solvent are used for moulding complex curvatures, insoluble binders are used where the sheet needs to retain tensile strength after impregnation e.g. in pultrusion.

APPLICATIONS

Since the fibres used for nonwovens are relatively short and randomly arranged, structural applications are few. The major applications are non structural. Nonwovens are used for the following non structural applications: surface finishing, fire protection, electrical conductivity, EMI/RFI shielding, and chemical resistance.

Surface Finishing

Surface finishing of composites is usually achieved using a gel coat in combination with a glass tissue to produce a resin rich surface. The use of a glass tissue with carbon or aramid reinforcements can cause problems of delamination of the surface due to, for example, differences in thermal expansion/contraction rates. The lower densities of carbon or aramid compared with glass means that surface tissues with much lower areal weights may be used. One particular application for carbon fibre tissue is for surfacing X-ray transparent composites where glass cannot be used because of its X-ray opacity.

Fire Resistance

A nonwoven material designed to improve fire performance is produced from a mixture of glass or other high temperature fibres with an ICI layer silicate mineral called M729 [1]. The silicate coats the fibres and forms a bond between the fibres, this results in a sheet of material which has excellent resistance to flame. An untreated

glass fabric is melted at about 600°C and hence loses integrity when subjected to a gas flame, a treated glass/M729 nonwoven retains integrity up to a temperature of about 1,000°C. In composites the material is used on the surface to prevent penetration by flame and to protect the underlying major reinforcements. In a fire the resin burns away but the fire resistant nonwoven remains intact and hence acts as a flame barrier.

One particular application is in the production of composite fire dampers [2] these operate as a safety valve, closing pipework when operated via a flame sensor

(Fig. 3)

A composite model incorporating several layers of flame resistant nonwoven with a fire resistant polyester resin, has been tested and approved at a temperature of up to 750°C for in excess of 50 mins. (Fig. 3)

Electrical Conductivity

Nonwovens provide a cost effective method of placing electrically conductive layers in composite. Conductive fibres (carbon or metals) are usually expensive, so the minimum amount to achieve the desired properties must be used.

Hybrids of conductive and non-conductive fibres are used on the surface of composites to produce predetermined surface resistivity values. The major reason for producing composites with electrically conductive surfaces is for protection from static discharge. Static electricity can be a severe problem in potentially explosive environments, e.g. coal mining, petrochemical production and powder handling; if the plant in this environment has electrically conductive surfaces and is earthed the plant is static safe. Materials with a surface resistivity of less than $10^5 \Omega \square$ are defined as being electrically conductive [3 - 5]. A typical hybrid to achieve this level consists of 80% E glass and 20% carbon fibre, chemical pipework produced with this material as a surface tissue has a surface resistivity of $20 \Omega \square$. When producing composites with a conductive surface by this method thick gel coats should be avoided, individual sections should be wired for continuity and the whole structure should be earthed. A related area is protection for lightning strike in this application highly conductive materials produced either from 100% carbon fibre or nickel coated carbon fibre should be used.

Resistive Heating

When a current is passed through a conductor, the temperature of the conductor increases, this is the principle of resistive heating. When applied to composites it is achieved by laminating a conductive layer, e.g. carbon fibre, between two insulating layers (usually glass). For demonstration purposes a panel 250 x 57 x 5 mm was produced using a carbon fibre nonwoven between two sheets of 900 g/m² CSN in Derakane 470 - 36 vinyl ester resin, brass electrodes were connected to each end of the carbon layer. The relationships between time and temperature at RV and between applied voltage and a maximum temperature at IA were determined. (Figs. 4 and 5)

Fig. 4 Temperature vs Time for heating panel at 12v/1A

Fig. 5 Temperature vs applied voltage for heating panel at constant 1A

From the above results it can be seen that the temperature rises gradually to its maximum value and then remains constant, also the maximum temperature reached is directly proportional to the applied voltage. This property suggests applications in which a thermostatic control can be achieved by using a temperature sensor to vary the applied voltage.

Perhaps the most interesting use of this technique in composites is the heating of composite tooling. The method is currently being assessed with various moulds including some fairly large moulds, e.g. those used in the production of small craft.

EMI/RFI Shielding

Perhaps the most important application of electrical conductivity in composites is for shielding from electromagnetic or radio frequency interference (EMI/RFI). Almost all plastics are transparent to EMI/RFI since they are electrical insulators. To provide a shield against EMI/RFI an electrical conductor is required; in composites this is achieved either by coating or painting the finished article with a

conductive (usually metal) paint or by the incorporation of conductive reinforcements of fillers. EMI/RFI shielding is needed for electrical equipment housings to prevent emission of unwanted signals and to protect the equipment from interference from external sources.

In the USA legislation now exists to limit the emission of EMI/RFI from computers and peripheral devices [6].

Shielding effectiveness for attenuation is expressed as the logarithm of the ratio of energy penetrating the shield to the incident energy, thus a shielding level of 35 dB means that over 99.9% of the core energy is stopped. For sheet materials the level of shielding effectiveness may be approximated from the following equation [7]:

$$SE_{dB} = 20 \log \frac{Z_w}{4Z_b}$$

Where SE = attenuation in decibels

Z_w = impedance in air (approx. 337)

Z_b = impedance of shield in ohms per square
(surface resistivity)

For a 100% carbon fibre nonwoven with surface resistivity of $2 \Omega/\square$ this gives a predicted attenuation of 33 dB.

One method of testing the level of shielding is the shielded box technique, in which one face of a box containing a sensor is made of the material to be tested. A measured signal is aimed at the test face and the attenuation measured by comparing the signal with the results from a sensor inside the box. A test panel containing a 60 g/m^2 layer of carbon fibre nonwoven was tested by this method and gave the results below (Fig. 6):

Fig. 6 EMI Shielding Results, Composite Panel
Containing a 60 g/m² Carbon Fibre Nonwoven

The amount of carbon fibre required is expected to be lower than the 60 g/m² used in this example, higher levels of carbon fibre gave no appreciable increase in shielding. The essential requirement appears to be a continuously conductive layer, the thickness of this layer is less important.

The use of a conductive nonwoven in the composite gives a permanent shield which cannot be destroyed by abrasion, weathering or delamination for the life of the composite. The shielding layer is added during the moulding of the composite so that difficult after processing is avoided.

The main component in shielding is the reflection of the wave, this can be useful in its own right. Conductive nonwovens are used as the reflective surface layers for items such as satellite TV dishes.

Chemical Resistance

Glass reinforced composites are very widely used in chemical engineering applications because of its excellent chemical resistance in comparison with metals. In certain environments, however, GRP is prone to stress corrosion which can result in sudden catastrophic failure. The most difficult chemical environments are strong bases and strong hot acids particularly hydrofloric, in these environments any failure of the gel coat can lead to a very rapid attack on the glass reinforcement. Carbon fibre has superior chemical resistance to glass including special corrosion resistance glasses [8]. The use of a carbon fibre nonwoven instead of a glass surfacing tissue can improve the resistance of the composite to those chemicals which most readily attack glass.

CONCLUSIONS

Nonwovens provide a route for the incorporation of lightweight layers of high performance fibres in composites. Where the desired properties are mostly non structural, nonwovens are an efficient way of modifying composite properties.

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